

Brunia noduliflora

Cone Stompie

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 1.5 m in height

Distribution:

Brunia noduliflora occurs from the Cederberg southwards to the Cape Peninsula and eastwards as far as the Cockscomb in the Groot Winterhoek Mountains of the Eastern Cape, at altitudes from near sea level to approximately 1 500 m.

Importance:

Brunia noduliflora is the most widespread species in the subgenus *Brunia* and occurs across diverse fynbos habitats in the Cape Floristic Region. Its broad ecological range makes it valuable for studying diversification and adaptation within the Bruniaceae.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 39.88 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 16.91 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.72 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.40% [Single: 47.0%, Duplicated: 50.0%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 30 437.33 kilobases

Contig number: 325

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